

On the Equivalence of Doehlert and Equiradial Designs in Modeling the GDP Growth of Nigerian Economy

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Abstract

The study 'on the equivalence of Doehlert and Equiradial Designs in modeling the GDP growth of Nigerian economy' was studied using quadratic model. Second-order designs were used in the analyses with radius of 1.0 and they include; Doehlert, Inscribed and Equiradial Designs. These designs were considered with additions of centre points from 1 to 5 inclusive. The study evaluated the equivalence of Doehlert and Equiradial Designs and proposed an equivalence equation of Doehlert Design (DD) and Equiradial Design (ED) with A-optimality. It was revealed that A-optimality of DD and that of ED decreases as the centre points increases. The proposed measure revealed that the two designs were equivalent and when the A-optimality of one of the designs is known, the A-optimality of the other can be obtained and vice versa. It was also revealed that the equiradial design for $n=6$ with 1 centre point is better than the doehlert design. The sum of square error value of equiradial design is less than that of doehlert design by 0.000222, while the doehlert design was found better than the inscribed design by 0.052816. As the centre points increases, it was observed that the sum of square errors of these designs increased significantly. It was therefore recommended among others, that the proposed Equivalence Equation of A-optimality can be used in obtaining the A-optimality of Doehlert Design when that of Equiradial Design is known and vice versa.

Keywords: Equiradial, Doehlert, Inscribed designs, Equivalence equation, Sum of square error.

1. Introduction

A second order model is a model in which the highest power of the control variable is 2. It is also called a quadratic model. The complete 3^k factorial designs and the central composite designs are used in modeling second-order functions in Response Surface Methodology. Obviously, when there is sign of curvature in the response function, attention is shifted to central composite designs, whose design points include the factorial points, the axial points and the centre point runs. It addresses the curvature experienced in the system. The 3^k is also appropriate in the modeling of second-order functions, but due to its large number of design points, hence central composite design (Box-Wilson design) became prominent in analyzing the model with curvature. Equiradial designs have also proven to be an alternative in modeling second-order response functions. Doehlert Design (DD) design is an alternative and very useful experimental design for second-order models. It is a uniform shell design proposed by Doehlert in the year 1970 for $k=2$ factors

design. Doehlert designs are easily applied to optimize variables and offer advantages in relation to Central Composite Designs (CCD) and Box-Behnken Designs (BBD). Doehlert designs are regular simplex like geometric figure, formed a $k+1$ equally spaced point in a k -dimensional space of equilateral triangle to form a hexagonal shape. This design begins from an equilateral triangle of lengths 1. To construct a regular hexagon (six-sided shape) with 1 centre point (0,0), then $N = n+1$ center point, where n = the radial point obtained from the shape of the design, hence, $n=6$, making $N=7$ sized design. The design points of a Doehlert design are: (1, 0), (0.5, 0.866), (0,0), (-0.5, 0.866), (-1, 0), (-0.5, -0.866) and (0.5, -0.866). The points on the hexagon, which is to say the 6 outer points lie on a circle of radius 1. It is a spherical design. It has an advantage of fewer number of experimental runs over the Central Composite Designs and the advantage over Equiradial Designs is that it can be modeled in more than two factors. Equiradial Design (ED) is an alternative second-order design in modeling second-order response functions. It is a design that is made up of more than one set of points such that each point in a set has an equal distance from the centre of the design region. It is a k factor design used as an alternative second-order design to the popularly encountered central composite design. In two-dimensions, the equiradial design has five points in a set defined for radius $\rho \geq 1$ from the centre of the design. This design is a spherical design that have equal axial distance from the design centre. It starts with a pentagon of equally spaced points and this design is augmented by the addition of centre points. Every design commences with the initial addition of a centre point (0,0) and the centre point can be increased if the initial one added lack fit, then the design can be augmented to fit the model under study. Central Composite Design (CCD) is class of design proposed Box and Wilson (1951) which can be easily constructed hence it being widely used. This design comprises of three portions which include the full or fractions of 2^k factorials points with the $2k$ axial points i^{th} pair given as (0,0, ...,0, α ,0, ...,0) and (0,0, ...,0,- α ,0, ...,0) where α and $-\alpha$ occur in the i^{th} spot in the k -vector and centre point n_0 of the form (0,0, ...,0). The equivalence in the estimation power of Doehlert Design, Inscribed Central Composite Design and Equiradial Design of axial distance of 1.0 have not been so clearly stated in the literatures. this work wants to bring to a limelight how Doehlert design will behave in comparison with equiradial design and inscribed CCD. The study used Doehlert Design, Inscribed Design and Equiradial Design all of radius of 1.0 in modelling the GDP growth of Nigeria economy. The study investigated if any of these designs are equivalent in their estimation using, sum of square error, D-optimality, and A-optimality to evaluate the effectiveness of these designs and least square method was used to estimate the model parameters. Since there have not been evidence of the performances of equiradial designs over the doehlert design and the two designs have not been used alongside Inscribed CCD in modeling the GDP of Nigeria, hence this work was designed to fill this existing knowledge gap. Kiefer and Wolfowitz (1959), in their contribution to the solution on optimal designs, reviewed the work done by Smith (1918) who was arguably the first to state a criterion and achieved optimal solutions for problems in regression analysis. The criterion Smith proposed and later developed was “minimizing the maximum prediction variance of any predicted value (obtained by using the regression function) over the experimental space.” This criterion was later reviewed and named Global Optimality Criterion, popularly called the G-optimality criterion by Olamide, et. al (2020) reviewed the concept of maximizing the determinant of the information matrix $X'X$ which pays much attention on the quality of the estimates of the model parameters. The above criterion was called D-optimality by Kiefer and Wolfowitz. Alhaddad, et. al. (2020) applied the Doehlert design for the removal of radium from the aqueous solution by cross-linked phenoxycalixpyrrole-polymer using Ba(II) as a model. Many efforts have been applied to decontaminate radium from aqueous media in order to

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meet the increasing water demand of the population. Hence a new polymer based on cross-linked phenoxyalixpyrrole was designed in solid/liquid extractions to remove radium from aqueous solutions.

Iwundu (2016a), laid emphasis on second-order N-point spherical response surface methodology designs and their effectiveness. The designs are seen to be comparable to with second-order response variables like central composite designs. The D-efficiencies of the equiradial variables with design radius of 1.0. Iwundu and Onu (2017), used the ideas of the D- and G-optimality and efficiency to propose two measures of the similarity of a design, known as D-Absolute Deviation (D-AD) and G-Absolute Deviation (G-AD). It was found that the values of these two proposed measures are zero if the pairs of designs are identical. Wonu, et al. (2023), equiradial design is a design that consists of sets of points arranged such that each point in a set has an equal distance from the design center. This is a class of $k=2$ factors design that was proposed by Box and Hunter (1957). Bezerra et al. (2008) stated that this distance is common in the circle such that, $\sum_{i=1}^k x_i^2 = \rho^2$, for $u = 1, 2, \dots, N$. This implies that the columns of ones and the columns corresponding to $x_1^2, x_2^2, \dots, x_l^2$ in the X-matrix for a quadratic model are linearly dependent which results in a singular information matrix, (Khuri & Cornell 1996 and Hibbert, 2012). Onu et al., (2022), while studying the Estimation of Parameters and Optimality of Second-Order Spherical Designs Using Quadratic Function Relative to Non-Spherical Face centered CCD presented a model for varying axial distances. It was observed that the sum of square error of the non-spherical face centered CCD with axial distance of 1.0 for radial point $n=5$ with 1 centre point is zero (0), while its spherical equiradial design counterpart with axial distance of 1.0 has a sum of square error of 0.0031 and variance of 0.00052. Oyejola et. al. (2015), made a comparative study of five variables of central composite design (SCCD, RCCD, OCCD, Slope-R, FCC) in response surface methodology (RSM) using the D-optimality, A-optimality, G-optimality, and IV-optimality criteria. Onu, et al. (2022), studied Estimation of Parameters and Optimality of Second-Order Spherical Designs using Quadratic Function Relative to Non-Spherical Face centered CCD. The study found that the sum of square error of the non-spherical face centered CCD with axial distance of 1.0 for radial point $n=5$ with 1 centre point is zero (0), while its spherical equiradial design counterpart with axial distance of 1.0 has a sum of square error of 0.0031 and variance of 0.00052, equiradial design with axial distance of 1.414 has a sum of square error of 2250.79 and variance of 375, inscribed central composite design with axial distance of 1.0 has a sum of square error of 0.069 and variance 0.012 and circumscribed central composite design with axial distance of 1.414 has sum of square error of 1275.26 and variance 212.54.

2. Materials and Methods

The study employed the methodology as applied in Onu, et al. (2023) as follows:

The quadratic model to be used is given as:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_{12}x_1x_2 + \beta_{11}x_1^2 + \beta_{22}x_2^2 + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where y represents the response variable, which is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Nigeria from 2012 to 2022, spanning an eleven (11) year period.

One of the designs to be employed in this research is the equiradial design of radial point 1.0, whose design points are obtained according to the formula as seen in Iwundu and Onu (2017),

$$x_1 = \rho \cos\left(\theta + \frac{2\pi u}{n}\right) \text{ and } x_2 = \rho \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2\pi u}{n}\right); u = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1 \quad (2)$$

where x_1 represents the values in the first row of the design D_5 and the x_2 represents the values in the second row of the design D_5 .

The parameters and the optimality criteria for the Equiradial and Inscribed designs for $n=5$, with $c = 1 - 5$ centre points.

Response Surface Methodology is mathematically defined as

$$y = \phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, \beta) \quad (3)$$

This is a general form of a statistical model. The Quadratic model having all the parameters represented will be applied in this study and the Quadratic model in (1) is given generally as seen:

$$y = \beta_0 + \left(\sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_i\right) + \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j X_j\right) + \left(\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{i < j}^k \beta_{ij} X_i X_j\right) + \left(\sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} X_i^2\right) + \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{jj} X_j^2\right) + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

which is written in a reduced form to suit the study and it can be presented in matrix form as

$$y = X\beta + \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

where X is an $N \times P$ matrix, y is an $N \times 1$ vector of observed responses, β is the $P \times 1$ vector of unknown parameters and $\varepsilon \sim N(0, \delta^2)$ is the error term that was distributed in a random form. From equation (3) ϕ is unknown and represents the real functional relationship between the response y (GDP of Nigeria) and the explanatory variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

The parameters and the optimality criteria for the Doehlert, Equiradial and Inscribed designs for $n=6$, with $c = 1 - 5$ centre points.

The parameters of these models will be estimated alongside their Alphabetic Optimality Criteria. The least square equation which will be used in the estimation of the parameters for both models is given as

$$\underline{\hat{\beta}} = \left(\frac{X'X}{N}\right)^{-1} X'Y \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{\hat{\beta}}$ is an $N \times 1$ vector, given as $(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_{12}, \beta_{11}, \beta_{22})'$ and $\left(\frac{X'X}{N}\right)^{-1}$ is the inverse of the normalized information matrix and N is the number of Design size.

Application of D-efficiency Absolute Deviation (D-AD) Criterion

The methodology for this D-AD criterion was developed by Iwundu and Onu in the year 2017. It is given as

$$|D_{eff}(\xi_{11}) - D_{eff}(\xi_{12})| \leq |D_{eff}(\xi_{21}) - D_{eff}(\xi_{22})|. \quad (7)$$

also

$$\text{If } |D_{eff}(\xi_{11}) - D_{eff}(\xi_{12})| = 0, \quad (8)$$

then design ξ_{11} and design ξ_{12} are similar in optimality property. The equation (7) is where this work will base its comparison.

Sum of Square Errors of these designs for increasing centre point (1-5) inclusive

For each of these designs (Doehlert, Equiradial and Inscribed Designs) with each centre point 1, the estimate of the sum of square errors of the quadratic regression equation would be obtained according to Onu et al. (2022), as shown below:

The sum of square error is given as

$$\sum \varepsilon_i^2 = \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (9)$$

Propose Equivalence Equation of A-optimality (EEA) of Doehlert and Equiradial Designs.

Recall that A-optimality between two designs is given as

$$tr(m_1) < tr(m_2) \quad (10)$$

If equation (10) is true, it is said that design m_1 is better than design m_2 based on A-optimality criterion. The developed methodology proposed in this work for the equivalence of A-optimality of Doehlert and Equiradial designs of radius of 1.0 is given as

$$|tr(m_1) - tr(m_2)| = |\omega| - |\gamma| = Constant \quad (11)$$

is the proposed equation, to be called the equivalence equation of A-optimality of DD and ED. where DD is the Doehlert Design and ED is the Equiradial Design. From equation (11) m_1 is the normalized information matrix of ED, while m_2 is the normalized information matrix of DD, while $|\cdot|$ is known as absolute value, tr means trace and ω is the $tr(m_1)$ and γ is the $tr(m_2)$. Then from equation (11), we obtain,

$$|\omega| = |\gamma| + Constant \quad (12)$$

While, making $|\gamma|$ the subject of formula, we obtain

$$|\gamma| = |\omega| - Constant \quad (13)$$

Equation (12) can be used to obtain the A-optimality of ED when the A-optimality of DD is known, while, equation (13) can be used to obtain the A-optimality of DD when that of ED is known. The proposed equation (11) which is the fundamental equation to (12) and (13) will need further numerical verification and extension to other designs for further studies.

3 Results and Discussion

Doehlert Design (DD) for 1 to 5 centre points

The design matrix for Doehlert Design for 1 centre point is given as

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 1.0000 & 1.0000 & 0 & 0 & 1.0000 & 0 \\ 1.0000 & 0.5000 & 0.8660 & 0.4330 & 0.2500 & 0.7500 \\ 1.0000 & -0.5000 & 0.8660 & -0.4330 & 0.2500 & 0.7500 \\ 1.0000 & -1.0000 & 0 & 0 & 1.0000 & 0 \\ 1.0000 & -0.5000 & -0.8660 & 0.4330 & 0.2500 & 0.7500 \\ 1.0000 & 0.5000 & -0.8660 & -0.4330 & 0.2500 & 0.7500 \\ 1.0000 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Similarly, designs will be constructed for Equiradial and Inscribed Designs from 1 to 5 centre points and for axial distance of $n=6$, (Onu et al. 2021). All the results obtained are tabulated in the following tables.

Comparison of Inscribed CCD and Equiradial Designs for $n=5$ and 1-5 centre points

Table 2 Comparison of Inscribed and Equiradial Designs for $n=5$, for increasing center points

C P	DESIGNS			D-Optimal		A-Optimal	
	DD	INSD	ED	INSD	ED	INSD	ED
1	0.0778	1.6910	1.6910	1.1660	2.6129	2.5668	2.5621
	0.4236	0.2070	0.4074	$\times 10^{-4}$	$\times 10^{-4}$		
	-0.1397	0.2787	0.1115				
	0.2438	-0.2818	-0.2993				
	1.3880	-0.6521	-0.4175				
	1.8586	0.2194	-0.1416				
2	0.0996	1.0253	1.0253	9.2480	2.0724	2.3429	2.3389
	0.4842	0.2415	0.4757	$\times 10^{-5}$	$\times 10^{-4}$		
	-0.1576	0.3411	0.1303				
	0.2786	-0.3288	-0.3480				
	1.5756	0.1867	0.4600				
	2.1134	1.2194	0.7827				

3	0.1142	0.8179	0.8179	6.2257 $\times 10^{-5}$	1.3951 $\times 10^{-4}$	2.1751	2.1716
	0.5447	0.2760	0.5438				
	-0.1773	0.3958	0.1489				
	0.3135	-0.3757	-0.3973				
	1.7703	0.5672	0.8794				
	2.3754	1.7533	1.2485				
4	0.1249	0.7198	0.7198	4.0946 $\times 10^{-5}$	9.1756 $\times 10^{-5}$	2.0445	2.0414
	0.6052	0.3105	0.6119				
	-0.1970	0.4486	0.1676				
	0.3483	-0.4227	-0.4467				
	1.9690	0.8385	1.1896				
	2.6413	2.1763	1.6050				
5	0.1394	0.6636	0.6636	2.7200 $\times 10^{-5}$	6.0954 $\times 10^{-5}$	1.9401	1.9372
	0.6657	0.3450	0.6800				
	-0.2167	0.5008	0.1862				
	0.3831	-0.4697	-0.4962				
	2.1639	1.0679	1.4579				
	2.9035	2.5565	1.9196				

Comparison of Doehlert Design, Inscribed CCD and Equiradial Design for n=6 and 1-5 centre points

Table 3 Comparison of Doehlert, Inscribed and Equiradial Designs for n=6, for increasing center points

C P	DESIGNS			D-Optimal			A-Optimal		
	DD	INSD	ED	DD	INSD	ED	DD	INSD	ED
1	Parameter estimates $\hat{\theta} \times 1.0e^7$								
	0.0778	0.0713	0.0775	2.5815 $\times 10^{-4}$	1.3847 $\times 10^{-4}$	2.5845 $\times 10^{-4}$	2.6071	2.5858	2.6072
	0.4236	-0.2724	0.4251						
	-0.1397	0.3553	-0.1379						
	0.2438	0.1225	0.2392						
	1.3880	1.2858	1.3880						
	1.8586	2.0970	1.8590						

2	0.0996	0.0959	0.0994	2.3172	1.2428	2.3198	2.4062	2.3876	2.4063
	0.4842	-0.3112	0.4858	$\times 10^{-4}$	$\times 10^{-4}$	$\times 10^{-4}$			
	-0.1576	0.4058	-0.1575						
	0.2786	0.1398	0.2734						
	1.5756	1.4550	1.5754						
	2.1134	2.3818	2.1137						
3	0.1142	0.1114	0.1141	1.7145	9.1951	1.7165	2.2500	2.2334	2.2501
	0.5447	-0.3501	0.5465	$\times 10^{-4}$	$\times 10^{-5}$	$\times 10^{-4}$			
	-0.1773	0.4565	-0.1772						
	0.3135	0.1572	0.3076						
	1.7703	1.6334	1.7701						
	2.3754	2.6759	2.3757						
4	0.1249	0.1226	0.1248	1.2149	6.5155	1.2163	2.1250	2.1101	2.1251
	0.6052	-0.3890	0.6073	$\times 10^{-4}$	$\times 10^{-5}$	$\times 10^{-4}$			
	-0.1970	0.5073	-0.1969						
	0.3483	0.1746	0.3418						
	1.9690	1.8161	1.9688						
	2.6413	2.9745	2.6416						
5	0.1394	0.1374	0.1393	8.5619	4.5972	8.5818	2.0227	2.0092	2.0228
	0.6657	-0.4279	0.6680	$\times 10^{-5}$	$\times 10^{-5}$	$\times 10^{-5}$			
	-0.2167	0.5580	-0.2166						
	0.3831	0.1921	0.3760						
	2.1639	1.9951	2.1637						
	2.9035	3.2694	2.9038						

D-Optimal Absolute Deviation (D-AD) of the designs

Table 4: Application of D-Optimal Absolute Deviation (D-AD) criterion

n = 6	Doehlert Design (DD)	Inscribed Design (INSD)	Equiradial Design (ED)	DD/INSD	DD/ED	INSD/ED
	D-efficiency (%)	D-efficiency (%)	D-efficiency (%)	D-AD	D-AD	D-AD

1	25.23	22.75	25.24	2.48	0.01	2.49
2	24.78	22.34	24.79	2.44	0.01	2.45
3	23.57	21.25	23.57	2.32	0	2.32
4	22.25	20.06	22.26	2.19	0.01	2.20
5	20.99	18.93	21.00	2.06	0.01	2.07

Table 5: Sum of Square Error Analysis

Designs	Centre point	Design size	Sum of Square Error
Doehlert	1	7	0.485911
	2	8	1.547889*
	3	9	0.434543
	4	10	0.063172**
	5	11	0.434032
Equiradial	1	7	0.485689
	2	8	1.546521*
	3	9	0.432606
	4	10	0.061344**
	5	11	0.432445
Inscribed CCD	1	7	0.538727
	2	8	1.938783*
	3	9	0.837509
	4	10	0.470575**
	5	11	0.837921

Key: * poorest estimate, ** best estimate for each design and centre point.

Proposed Equivalence Equation of A-optimality of the Designs

Table 6: Proposed Equivalence Equation of A-optimality (EEA) of both Doehlert and Equiradial Designs

n = 6	A-Optimal	A-Optimal	A-Opt(1) – A-Opt(2)
	DD	ED	
1	2.6071	2.6072	0.0001
2	2.4062	2.4063	0.0001
3	2.2500	2.2501	0.0001
4	2.1250	2.1251	0.0001
5	2.0227	2.0228	0.0001

4 Discussion of Results

Based on the comparison of Inscribed CCD and Equiradial Designs for n=5 and 1-5 centre points

The study revealed that the Grand Mean of the Inscribed CCD was equal to the Grand Mean of Equiradial Design. This result is true for all centre points, for radial point of n=5 and axial distance of 1.0, while other parameters vary for varying design and varying centre points. The D-optimality of equiradial design for n=5 and 1 centre point is better than that of Inscribed CCD by **1.4469e-4**, also, the equiradial design for n=5 and 1 centre point is better than the Inscribed CCD on the bases of A-optimality by **4.7e-3**. This is true for all the centre points studied, nevertheless, the differences observed decreases as the centre point increases.

Based on the comparison of Doehlert Design, Inscribed CCD and Equiradial Design for n=6 and 1-5 centre points

It was observed that for radial point of n= 6, Inscribed CCD and Doehlert design gave grand means that slightly differs from that of equiradial design for 1 centre point, as the centre point increases, the grand mean of the Inscribed CCD differs more significantly, while the grand mean of the doehlert design begins to close ranks with that of equiradial design. This means that increasing the centre points augments the Doehlert design towards equiradial design. It was further revealed that the equiradial design performs better than the doehlert design with a difference of **3.0e-3**, while the doehlert design was found better than the Inscribed CCD based on the D-Optimality criterion. In the other hand, the Doehlert design was slightly better than the equiradial design with a difference of **1.0e-4** based on A-Optimality while the Equiradial design was found better than the Inscribed CCD for 1 centre point. As the centre point increases, the difference between the D-optimality of doehlert design and the equiradial design decreases. The study shows that the strength that was shown by doehlert design over the equiradial design for n=6 and 1 centre point on a constantly from 1-5 centre points with the value of 1.0e-4. This means that if one finds the A-optimality of equiradial design to be say 2.6072, needless of calculating the A-optimality of doehlert design using the normal method that may be seen to be long process. Rather, to obtain the

value of A-optimality of the doehlert design, simply subtract this said constant ($1.0e-4$) from the value of the already known value of A-optimality of the equiradial design (2.6072), also, if you have the A-optimality of doehlert design as 2.6071 and wish to obtain that of equiradial design, just add the constant ($1.0e-4$) to the already known value of A-optimality of doehlert design (2.6071). The Inscribed CCD in the other hand has shown to be inferior to these two designs. This result is in line to the findings of Iwundu and Onu (2017) that says, that the equiradial design of radial point of 1.414 and circumscribed CCD are better than the equiradial design of radial point of 1.0 and the inscribed CCD on the basis of D-, G-optimality criteria. The results showed that the equiradial design is better than the doehlert design on the basis of D-optimality, while the doehlert design is better than the equiradial design on the basis of A-optimality criterion.

Based on the D-Optimal Absolute Deviation (D-AD) of the designs

It was revealed that the A-optimality of Doehlert Design and that of Equiradial Design decreases as centre point increases. Also, the Proposed A-optimal Absolute Deviation (A-AD) used in measuring the equivalence of two designs shows a constant value of 0.0001 from 1-5 centre points inclusive. This means that Doehlert and Equiradial designs are equivalent. Which is to say they produce same or approximately same results.

Based on the Sum of Square Error Analysis

On the sum of square analysis, it was observed that the equiradial design for $n=6$ with 1 centre point is better than the doehlert design. The sum of square error value of equiradial design is less than that of doehlert design by 0.000222, while the doehlert design was found better than the inscribed design by 0.052816. As the centre points increases, it was observed that the sum of square errors these designs increases significantly. This result was in line to the result of Onu et al. (2022). It shows that the difference between the sum of square errors of equiradial designs with 1 and 2 centre points was 1.060852 and the difference between the sum of square error of doehlert design with 1 and 2 centre points was obtained as 0.061978.

Based on the Proposed Equivalence Equation of A-optimality (EEA) of both Doehlert and Equiradial Designs

The proposed EEA shows that Doehlert Design and Equiradial Design are equivalent as seen in table 4.19 above. This equivalence was not so visible by means of D-optimality, parameters, and sum of square error. The measure that showed this equivalence properly was the trace which led to proposing of the Equivalence Equation of A-Optmality. It was observed that the D-efficiency of the designs decreases as the centre point increases. The results of the D-AD show that Doehlert Design and Inscribed CCD are not identical, likewise the Inscribed CCD and the Equiradial designs. Whereas the Doehlert design and the Equiradial designs are found to be identical, most especially, at 3 centre point where the D-AD value was obtained to be zero (0). Other centre points from 1, 2, 4 and 5 gave constant D-AD value of 0.01.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the Grand Mean of the Inscribed CCD was equal to the Grand Mean of Equiradial Design. This result is true for all centre points, for radial point of $n=5$ and axial distance of 1.0, while other parameters vary for varying design and varying centre points. The D-optimality of equiradial design for $n=5$ and 1 centre point is better than that of Inscribed CCD by $1.4469e-4$, also, the equiradial design for $n=5$ and 1 centre point is better than the Inscribed CCD on the bases of A-optimality by $4.7e-3$. For radial point of $n=6$ and center point of 1, Inscribed CCD and Doehlert design gave grand means that slightly differ from that of equiradial design, but as the centre point increases, the grand mean of the Inscribed CCD differs more significantly, while the grand mean of the doehlert design begins to close ranks with that of equiradial design. This means that increasing the centre points augments the Doehlert design towards Equiradial design. It was further revealed that the equiradial design performs better than the doehlert design with a difference of $3.0e-3$, while the doehlert design was found better than the Inscribed CCD based on the D-Optimality criterion. Also, the D-efficiency of the designs decreases as the centre point increases. The results of the D-AD show that Doehlert Design and Inscribed CCD are not identical, likewise the Inscribed CCD and the Equiradial designs. Whereas the Doehlert design and the Equiradial designs are found to be identical, most especially, at 3 centre point where the D-AD value was obtained to be zero (0). Other centre points from 1, 2, 4 and 5 gave constant D-AD value of 0.01. finally, the proposed EEA suggests that the Doehlert Design and the Equiradial Designs are equivalent in their analyses.

Recommendations

Based on findings of this study, the following were recommended to Policy makers, Researchers, Government at all level and Statisticians.

1. Doehlert Design and Equiradial Design for radius of 1.0 are equivalent in their performance. That means the Equiradial design of radius of 1.0 can do/perform same functions as the Doehlert design too.
2. The proposed Equivalence Equation of A-optimality can be used in obtaining the A-optimality of Doehlert Design when that of ED is known and verse versa.
3. The grand means of Doehlert design becomes equivalent with the equiradial design as the centre point increases.

Contribution to Knowledge

The research work was able to add the following to the knowledge base

1. The Grand mean of Doehlert design becomes equivalent with the Equiradial design for increasing centre points.
2. The A-optimality is a better measure to show the equivalence of Doehlert and Equiradial designs.
3. The study was able to propose the Equivalence of Equiradial and the Doehlert Designs.

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